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FLORA OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN JSSAC, MYSURU

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have been known from pre-historic times and these are the backbone of traditional medicines. JSSAC has brought up a comprehensive herbal garden which constitutes more than 300 medicinal plants. In the present paper around 100 medicinal plants have been identified and distinguished based on part used to cure different ailments and also included Botanical name, family, part used, habit and medicinal uses of the plants.

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INTRODUCTION

India is known for its traditional medicinal systems—Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani. Medical systems are found mentioned even in the ancient Vedas and other scriptures. The Ayurvedic concept appeared and developed between 2500 and 500 BC in India (10). Medicinal plants are the backbone of traditional medicines. In India they are about 17000 species of higher plants of which approximately 8000 species are considered medicinal and used by village communities, particularly tribal communities, or in traditional medicinal systems such as the Ayurveda (9)

JSS Ayurveda College located at Sri ShivarathreeshwaraNagara, Mysuru, Karnataka, is situated at the foot of Chamundi hills, in the close vicinity of Lalithamahal hotel, Lalithadripuram road, Alanahalli, Mysuru. The 15 acres large campus is situated in serene outskirts under the foothills of Chamundi Hills, away from the hustle and bustle of the city. The college is surrounded by splendid Ayurveda herb garden from which most medicines are produced. The medicinal plants being integral part of Ayurvedic education, the college has brought up a comprehensive herbal garden which constitutes more than 300 medicinal plants.

Medicinal plants frequently used as raw materials for extraction of active ingredients which was used in the synthesis of different drugs. Like in case of laxatives, blood thinners, antibiotics and anti-malarial medications, contain ingredients from plants. Medicinal plants are an integral component of research developments in the pharmaceutical industry (9).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study are: The present study was carried out in JSSAC, Mysuru, which is an outskirts under the foothills of Chamundi Hills situated in north eastern part between 12.2911° N, 76.6952° E (Fig. 1)

Methodology: Periodical trips were carried out in different seasons during 2018-19. The details have been noted down in the field note book for future identification. The plant were identified based on characters with the help of standard flora (2). The identified plant specimen have been arranged based on the part used to cure different ailments with their respective family, botanical name, vernacular name. The families have been arranged according to Bentham and Hooker's system of classification (1).

RESULTS

The study reveals that around 100 medicinal plants have been identified and distinguished based on part used to cure different ailments and also included Botanical name, family, part used, habit and medicinal uses of the plants. Among them 37 herbs, 34 trees, 10 shrubs and 10 climbers.

The present study observed and categorised plants based on the different plant parts used, such as 02 rhizome, 07 roots, 11 barks, 31 leaves, 04 flowers, 18 fruits, 01 seed, 03 nuts and 15 whole plant.

Fig. 1: a) Karnataka map, b) Mysuru map, c) Route map of JSS ayurvedic college

Fig. 2. Plants list based on different plant parts used.

Table: 1: List of plant species according to different plant parts in JSSAC, Herbal garden.

RHIZOME			
Species	Family	Local name	Medicinal use
<i>Acoruscalamus</i>	Araceae	Baje	Rheumatism, rheumatic fever and inflamed joints
<i>Zingiberofficinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Shunti	Cough, common cold, fever, respiratory troubles, pain, headache, backache
ROOTS			
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Liliaceae	Satavari	Female personal problems
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Zingiberaceae	Arashina	Heartburn, Joint pain, stomach pain, Headache, ringworm
<i>Hemidesmusindicus</i>	Apocynaceae	Sogadeberu	Appetite loss, dyspepsia, fever, skin diseases, Chronic coughs
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	Convolvulaceae	Sweet Potato	Pitta, general weakness
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Fabaceae	Touch me not	Heels cuts and wounds in animals
<i>Plumbagoauriculata</i>	Plumbaginaceae	NeeliChitramula	Headache
<i>Withaniasomnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Ashwagandha	Asthma, diabetes, hypertension, fever, cold
BARK			
<i>Ficusreligiosa</i>	Moraceae	Arali	Jaundice, nose bleeding
<i>Homalocladiumplatycladum</i>	Polygonaceae	Jhanthalamara	Snake bites, injuries
<i>Muntingiacalabura</i>	Muntingiaceae	Gasagasemara	Antiseptic
<i>Plumeria alba</i>	Apocynaceae	Deva ganagle	Cough, fever
<i>Plumeriapudica</i>	Apocynaceae	Devvaganagle	Ulcers
<i>Pongamiapinnata</i>	Leguminaceae	Honge	Piles, skin diseases
<i>Santalum album</i>	Santalaceae	Gandha	Cold, cough, fever, skin diseases
<i>Saracaasoca</i>	Fabaceae	Ashoka	Female reproductive disorder
<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Lamiaceae	Teak	Fever, headache
LEAVES			
<i>Adhatodavastica</i>	Acantaceae	Adusoge	Ailments of respiratory tract
<i>Aeglemarmelos</i>	Rutaceae	Bela	Rich in insulin, Antidiabetic
<i>Aervalanata</i>	Amaranthaceae	Bilihimdisoppu	Cough, asthma, headache
<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>	Liliaceae	Aloevera	All skin diseases
<i>Alternantherasessilis</i>	Amaranthaceae	Honnagone	Beneficial for eye
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Mulluharave	Internal bleeding, female disorders
<i>Andrographispaniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Nelabevu	Cardiovascular disease, diabetes, hypertension
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Bevu	Head lice, fever, rheumatism, asthma, worm infestations, insecticide
<i>Basella alba</i>	Basellaceae	Basalesoppu	Gastritis
<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Brassicaceae	Wild cabbage	Rheumatism, clean wounds
<i>Bryophyllumpinnatum</i>	Crassulaceae	Kandukalinga	Antidiabetic
<i>Calotropisprocera</i>	Apocynaceae	Ekka	Asthama
<i>Centellaasiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Ondalaga	Promotes memory

<i>Cocculushirsutus</i>	Menispermaceae	Dagadiballi	Urinary diseases, Migraine
<i>Cymbopogoncitratu</i>	Graminae	Majjigehullu	Digestive problems, Aromatic, Insect repellent
<i>Cynodondactylon</i>	Poaceae	Garike	Laxative, coolant, expectorant
<i>Gymnemasylvestre</i>	Apocynaceae	Madhunaashini	Anti-inflammatory, Digestive, stomach ache
<i>Lantana camara</i>	Verbenaceae	Rojagida	Leprosy
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Lythraceae	Henna	Coloring agent, wound healing
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae	Mango	Wound healing, toothache
<i>Moringaoleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Nuggekai	Stomach pain, intestinal problems
<i>Murrayakoenigii</i>	Rutaceae	Curry	Astringent, cooling, aromatic
<i>Nephrolepisexaltata</i>	Nephrolepidaceae	Fern	Air purifier
<i>Nyctanthesarbor-tristis</i>	Oleaceae	Parijatha	Laxative, Anti-inflammatory , Natural kaja
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Labiatae	Tulasi	Cold, fever, bronchitis and cough
<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	Oxalidaceae	Hulisoppu	quench the thirst, fever
<i>Piper betle</i>	Piperaceae	White betel	Carminative, stomachic, aromatic, Menstrual pains
<i>Pistia</i>	Araceae	Antaragange	Kidney disorder
<i>Plectranthusaromaticus</i>	Lamiaceae	Doddapatre	Cough, fever, skin disease
<i>Stachytarpheta indica</i>	Verbenaceae	Kaduuttarani	Asthma
<i>Thujaoccidentalis</i>	Cupressaceae	Thuja	Respiratory problems
<i>Thevetiaperuviana</i>	Apocynaceae	Gantehoovu	Intermittent fever
FLOWERS			
<i>Buteamonosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Palasa	Kapha, bowel, eye diseases
<i>Chrysanthemum morifolium</i>	Asteraceae	Sevanthige	High Blood pressure, headache
<i>Leucasaspera</i>	Lamiaceae	Thumbe	Kapha, cold, fever,
<i>Rosa centifolia</i>	Rosaceae	Rose	Blood purifier
FRUITS			
<i>Annonasquamosa</i>	Annonaceae	Seethapala	Vermicide, insecticide
<i>Areca catechu</i>	Arecaceae	Betel	Digestive, increase stamina
<i>Artocarpusheterophyllus</i>	Moraceae	Halasu	Digestive, rich in potassium
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Caricaceae	Papaya	Gastrointestinal problems
<i>Citrus limon</i>	Rutaceae	Gajhanimbe	Digestive, stomachic, laxative, antiseptic, mosquito repellent
<i>Coccinia indica</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Tondekai	Eye infection, insect bite
<i>Dillenia indica</i>	Dilleniaceae	Elephant apple	Inflammation, bad odour from mouth
<i>Elettariacardamomum</i>	Zingiberaceae	Elachi	Nausea, vomiting, bad smell
<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	Ashwatta	Cough, skin disease, nausea
<i>Morindacitrifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Noni	Diabetes, high blood pressure, Viral and bacterial infections
<i>Phyllanthusemblica</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Bettadanelli	Treat constipation, reduce cough, purify blood, Vitamin C rich
<i>Psidiumguajava</i>	Myrtaceae	Guava	Hypertension, oral ulcer
<i>Punicagranatum</i>	Punicaceae	Pomegranate	Vomiting, and eye pain
<i>Solanummelongena</i>	Solanaceae	Badane	Toothache, infection
<i>Solanummigrum</i>	Solanaceae	Wild eggplant	Condiment, Treatment of piles, Dysentery
<i>Spondiasmombin</i>	Anacardiaceae	Amatekai	Diuretic
<i>Terminaliacatappa</i>	Combretaceae	Kaadubadam	Skin diseases
<i>Thespesiapopulnea</i>	Malvaceae	Bugrimara	Urinary problem
SEEDS			
<i>Ravenalamadagascariensis</i>	Strelitziaceae	Traveller plant	Anti-diabetic
NUTS			
<i>Cocosnucifera</i>	Arecaceae	Tenginmara	Chill, cooling agent
<i>Cycas revoluta</i>	Cycadaceae	Cycas	High blood pressure, headache
<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Piperaceae	Mensu	Cough, branchites
WHOLE PLANT			
<i>Achyranthesaspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Uttarani	Bleed, scorpion bite, snake bite
<i>Asclepiascurassavica</i>	Apocynaceae	Blood flower	bleeding wounds Warts
<i>Bombaxceiba</i>	Bombacaceae	Silk Cotton	Blood impurities, Pitta
<i>Cissusquadrangularis</i>	Vitaceae	Sanduballi	Strength bones, joints
<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Bhedhisoppu	Constipation, asthma
<i>Helicteresisora</i>	Malvaceae	Edmuribalmuri	Intestinal worms
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Malvaceae	Dasavala	Skin diseases, Fever, Fertility treatments
<i>Musa acuminata</i>	Musaceae	Banana	Fever, cough, digestion
<i>Nerium oleander</i>	Apocynaceae	Gangle	Scabies, eye disease
<i>Plumbagozeylanica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Chitramuli	Skin diseases, menstrual disorder
<i>Rutagraveolens</i>	Rutaceae	Nagadhali	Bug bite, Cold, fever, snakebite

<i>Saussureaobvallata</i>	Asteraceae	Brahma kamala	Liver disorder, bone ache
<i>Tinosporacordifolia</i>	Menispermaceae	Amruthaballi	Treat fever, cholera, diabetes, rheumatism
<i>Tradescantiazebrina</i>	Commelinaceae	Jew plant	Piles, blood in urinary tract
<i>Urticaurens</i>	Urticaceae	Nettle	Insect bites, heals cuts and wounds

DISCUSSION

Medicinal plants are the backbone of traditional medicine which have been deep rooted in India. Medicinal plants are an integral component of research developments in the pharmaceutical industry as a raw material to cure different ailments (9) and synthesis different drugs which have active ingredients of taxol, vincristine and morphine isolated from foxglove, periwinkle, yemand opium poppy, respectively (9).

Some of the medicinal plants have been reported in different papers in for example *Hemidesmusindicus* roots are carminative, appetizer, and used in the condition of pitta, burning sensation (5)(7). *Aralimara* is considered as sacred tree in India, its bark is inflammatory swellings, blood disorder and leprocy (4)(3). *Amruthaballi* is an anti-diabetic plant which is used to cure Type-2 diabetics (8). The stem and leaves of *Basellaalba* are sweet, cooling agent (6) and also useful as laxative in children and pregnancy women (7).

Biodiversity conservation is the only way to conserve highly medicinal plants due to its over exploitation. *Rauwolfiaserpentina* and *Helicteresisora* are the plants which have been listed under endangered categories.

CONCLUSION

Conservation is the only method to protect the plants. This survey has brought up interest and concern regarding that how each part of a particular plant has its own importance, majority of plants which was documented are tree species, which have high economic as well as medicinal value. Therefore in future studies, it is important to evaluate and extract active ingredient from the medicinal plants to prepare new synthetic drugs.

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REFERENCES

1. Bentham G., Hooker J.D. Genera Plantarum. Vols. 1-3. Reeve & Co., London, 1862-1883
2. Gamble JS. Flora of the Presidency of Madras, Vol. 1-3. Adlard & Sons Ltd., London, 1915; pp. 1-577
3. Gireesha, J., and Raju, N.S. (2013). Ethno botanical study of medicinal plants in BR hills region of Westren Ghats, Karnataka. *Asian journal of plant science and Research*. 3(5): 36-40.
4. Prabhat Kumar Rai and Lalramnghinglova, H. (2010). Ethnomedicinal plant resources of Mizoram, India: Implication of traditional knowledge in health care system. *Ethnobotanical leaflets*. 14: 274-305.
5. Prasanthkumar G.M, Shiddamallayya N. (2015). Survey of wild medicinal plants of Hassan district, Karnataka. *Journal of medicinal plants studies*. 4(1):91-102.
6. Rama Shankar and Rawat. M. S., (2013), conservation and cultivation of threatened and high valued medicinal plants in North east India. *International journal of biodiversity and conservation*. 5(9): 584-591.
7. Sala A.V, (2010). Indian medicinal plants VOL 1-5, 7th edition. Universities press.
8. Shiddamallayyan, N., Azra Yasmeen, Gopakumar. (2008). Hundred common forest medicinal plants of Karnataka in primary health care. *Indian journal of Traditional knowledge*. 9(1):90-95.
9. Singh R. Medicinal Plants: A Review. *Journal of Plant Sciences*. Special Issue: Medicinal Plants. Vol. 3, No. 1-1, 2015, pp. 50-55.
10. Subhose, V., P. Srinivas, and A. Narayana, "Basic principles of pharmaceutical science in Ayurvēda," *Bulletin of the Indian Institute of History of Medicine*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 83-92, 2005.

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